

OCCURRENCE OF PHRASEOLOGISMS IN SPEECH

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ANNOTATION

This article talks about German phraseology, scientists who contributed to the field of phraseology, Uzbek cognates of German phrases and their use in speech, German phraseology phenomenon of synonymy, antonymy, homonymy information about the meeting was given.

KEY WORDS: phraseologism, phraseological layer, synonym, antonym, homonymous expressions.

In linguistics, the phraseological layer and the field studying it is called phraseology. In turn, phraseology focuses on the study of the nature of phraseologisms, their categorical features, as well as the rules of how and in which case they are used in speech. The main tasks of phraseology are: to study the symbolic nature of phraseological units, to determine and describe their synonymy, antonymy, homonymy and variant compatibility, to distinguish phraseologisms from ordinary word combinations and to determine their specific role in speech. Phraseology is understood in two ways: narrow and broad. Understood in a broad sense, the science of phraseology includes proverbs, aphorisms, and wise words as well as phrases.

Phraseology as an independent branch of linguistics appeared in Russian linguistics in the 40s of the 20th century. The works of Russian scientists A.A. Potebnya, I.I. Sreznevsky, A.A. Shakhmatov were the basis for the formation of phraseology. Later, the study of the field of phraseology and its interpretation as a separate, independent science was emphasized in the works of Ye.D. Polivanov, S. Abakumov, L.A. Bulakhovsky and educational and methodological literature. However, the Russian scientist who made the greatest contribution to the development of this science is V.V. Vinogradov.

Scholars such as Sh. Rakhmatullayev, M. Sodikova, I. Kochkortoyev, A. Rafiyev studied phraseology in Uzbek linguistics on a large scale. In general, idioms are a unit of language that has been handed down from mouth to mouth by wise people for centuries, and they help to make speech attractive, somewhat expressive and colorful, and to express happiness, anger, pity or sarcasm more effectively. will give. As in all languages, German linguists pay special attention to the study of phraseology. Including U.Fiks, H.Burger, T.Shippan, D.Stepanova, I.I.Cherneshova, A.Rotkegel and others. The linguist Sh. Imyaminova studied and analyzed the phraseologisms existing in the German language in her research work. According to him, the most commonly used expressions in speech can be divided into two types. The first is phraseology that expresses the appearance of people, which can include very tall or, on the contrary, very short, very thin or very fat. [1] For example,

Eine lange Latte (long stick)

Ein langes Ende (no end)

As mentioned above, such phrases are mainly used in sarcastic, insulting sentences, and over time, these phrases become like nicknames. At first glance, it is not noticeable that these expressions are used in relation to a person. However, the word «lang» (long) in the phrase serves to reveal the overall meaning, because it is impossible to compare a person to a «stick» or an «infinite» thing.

In the Uzbek language, some expressions are used in relation to the appearance of a person. For example, «terak», «mirzaterak», «sinchalak», «sinchalak», «giant», «devkomat» and other similar words are used for tall and fat people. . It should be noted that the expressions listed above are used in colloquial and artistic style, not in official and scientific styles.

«Arslonbek» «If I called Saidakhon «sinchalak» then, later I corrected this mistake in front of Comrade Nasirov, I also corrected it at the general assembly of collective farmers. «I told you that you have energy and enthusiasm to lift the sky./»A. Qahhor, «Sinchalak»/

The second includes phraseology about intelligence, ability, life experience. The expressions «Einen Köpfchen haben» and «Einen offenen Kopf haben» are used to refer to people who are naturally intelligent and have a clear mind. The phrase «ein wandelendes Lexikon» is used to express the maturity of a person's all-round knowledge and abilities. [1]

In addition, there are such expressions in the German language that blindly translating them into other languages leads to the loss of their original meaning. The expression «Eine gemütliche Haut» refers to a person with a good heart, but if we translate it literally, it translates to «a good skin». The phraseology «Eine harte Nuss» is translated into Uzbek as «hard nut», and in fact it is used for a serious person.

Ich möchte mich nicht wie ein fünftes Rad am Wagen fühlen - I don't want to feel like an extra person. In this sentence, the phrase «fünftes Rad am Wagen» is used, which means to be the fifth wheel in a cart. In this case, the word extra wheel means extra person. In the Uzbek language, the expression « oshga pashsha bo'lmoq» is used in these cases, and in Russian, the expression «третий лишний» is used.

«When I went to Marziya's house, Dushan and Fazil were always the ones who were the fly in the ointment.» /A. Mukhtor, «Time is in my destiny»/

As in all languages, in German, phraseological units are grouped according to their meaning, that is, they are divided into antonyms, synonyms and homonyms. Phraseological synonymy is the use of two phrases in exactly the same sense, phraseological antonymy is phrases that are completely opposite to each other. Phraseological homonymy means two or more different meanings of the same form. Below are examples of synonyms of phrases:

The expressions «Auf Draht sein» and «über den Berg sein» have the same meaning: «to recover quickly, to recover». The expressions «alles auf eine Karte setzen», «etwas auf eigene Faust tun», «etwas auf gut Glück tun» mean «do something at your own risk»;

The expressions «das Herz auf dem rechten Fleck haben» and «kein Unmensch sein» give the same meaning «to be truly human». In German, phraseological units related to the concepts of luck and bad luck are often used in speech. For example, the expressions «Schwein haben» and «mehr Glück als Verstand haben» mean «to be lucky», «to be lucky» and constitute synonymy. In contrast to the listed expressions, we can give examples of the following phraseologisms:

«auf keinen grünen Zweig kommen» (bad luck, bad luck); «sich den Hals brechen» and «Pech haben». In turn, these expressions have become synonymous with each other. In

addition, the expressions «ein Pechvogel sein» (an unlucky, poor person) and «ein Glückskind sein» (a lucky person) are also antonyms.

Er ist ein Glüc

Er ist ein Glückskind, weil er alle seine Ziele erreicht hat. (He is a lucky man because he has achieved all his goals)

Phraseological homonyms are homonyms that occur between compounds that have a figurative effect, which often occur between two phrases, for example:

a) Hals über Kopf – 1. to be dizzy

Hals über Kopf – 2. apil-tapil, in haste;

b) j-n oder etwas zu Fall bringen – 1. to fail someone; to ruin;

j-n oder etwas zu Fall bringen – 2. to make someone dizzy

The peculiarity of phraseological units is that they always express a figurative meaning, there is an answer to a question in a sentence, and they are part of a sentence. It is not allowed to round the words in the phrase separately.

In conclusion, it can be said that the language never stops developing and moving, therefore phraseologisms also increase over time, and new expressions begin to appear, adapting to the times. The phraseological layer of each language is formed based on the culture, customs and way of life of the nation belonging to that language.

References:

- 1.Sh. Imyaminova, Phraseology of the German language. TASHKENT-2011
2. Z. Kuvonov, Study of phraseologisms in German linguistics. Central Asian Research Journal For Interdisciplinary Studies (CARJIS), 2022
- 3.<https://audiobook.uz/blogs/news/frazeologik-iboralar-va-ularga-misollar>
- 4.Shuhrat o'g'li, K. Q., Shuhrat o'g'li, K. Q., & Xusanova, Z. (2023). O 'ZBEK VA NEMIS TILLARIDA MOTAM BILAN BOG 'LIQ SHAXS, NARSA, PREDMET VA JOY NOMLARI. Scientific journal of the Fergana State University, (4), 65-65.
- 5.Kaxarov, Q., & Abdurazzakova, M. (2023). SHAXSLARARO MULOQOTDA NOVERBAL MULOQOTNING AHAMIYATI. Scientific journal of the Fergana State University, (3), 114-114.
- 6.Kaxarov, Q., & Mustafoyeva, S. M. S. (2023). O 'ZBEK VA NEMIS TILLARIDA SEN/SIZ MUROJAAT SHAKLLARI. Scientific journal of the Fergana State University, (3), 105-105.